

SOMATIC SYMPTOMS OF DEPRESSION AMONG PATIENTS WITH IRRITABLE BOWEL SYNDROME (IBS)

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to explore the prevalence of somatic symptoms associated with depression in patients with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) within the Georgian population. IBS was diagnosed according to the Rome IV diagnostic criteria. A total of 287 patients were screened, and 89 were included in the study. Depression was evaluated using the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HRSD21), and 64 patients (71.91%) were diagnosed with depression. Of these, 24 patients (37.5%) had moderate depression, while 40 patients (62.5%) were diagnosed with severe depression. There is a strong link between IBS and depression, making it crucial to evaluate IBS patients for signs of depression, particularly when these symptoms are masked.

Keywords: IBS, Depression, Somatic, HDRS-21.

Introduction

Irritable bowel syndrome is a functional disorder of the gastrointestinal system, affecting approximately 11% of the global population, with its prevalence varying significantly both within and across different countries and cultures (6). The exact cause of irritable bowel syndrome is unknown, but chronic stress, along with individual and genetic factors, is believed to contribute to the activation of a complex psychoimmunological mechanism, influencing the development of intestinal disorders (9).

It is characterized by abdominal pain and altered bowel habits. Patients with this condition often experience diarrhea, constipation, or a combination of both. The exact causes of IBS remain unclear, but researchers suggest a combination of biological and psychosocial factors may play a role (2).

Patients with irritable bowel syndrome frequently suffer from coexisting mental health conditions, with depression being the most prevalent. Research indicates that individuals with IBS are three times more likely to develop depression compared to those without the condition (5). In IBS, the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, which regulates the body's response to stress, becomes dysregulated. This dysregulation is a central pathophysiological mechanism also present in depression, which scholars believe accounts for the high prevalence of depression in individuals with IBS (8).

Patients with IBS who are diagnosed with depression often exhibit heightened bodily anxiety, hypochondriacal beliefs, and a fear of illness. Research indicates that irritable bowel syndrome is clinically linked to an exaggerated concern about health and illness (1). In addition to this, the quality of life for patients experiencing depression declines significantly, worsening their psychological state. Alleviating depressive symptoms plays a crucial role in enhancing their quality of life (6).

In patients with irritable bowel syndrome, depression is presented with both psychological and somatic symptoms. Hamilton Depression Scale is frequently used as a diagnostic tool. Its key advantage lies in its ability to assess the somatic aspects of depression. This is particularly significant in light of recent researches indicating that depression, especially when accompanied by somatic symptoms, remains underdiagnosed in up to 50% of cases, even in developed countries (7).

Somatic symptoms can be confusing or masked and as authors note, they may also heighten the risk of disease recurrence (4). Individuals with depression often describe somatic symptoms as unpleasant and distressing bodily sensations. These symptoms may be perceived as localized to specific body parts or organs, or they can affect the entire body (3).

This paper employs Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS-21), which measures both psychological and somatic symptoms, to investigate the relationship between depression and irritable bowel syndrome and assess the prevalence of somatic symptoms of depression among IBS patients.

This study confirms the comorbidity between IBS and depression, as evidenced by both psychological and somatic complaints in the affected population. Particular emphasis was placed on the prevalence of somatic symptoms, as these are often overlooked by physicians during patient interviews, making it more challenging to accurately diagnose depression.

Methodology

This prospective observational study was carried out in the Gastroenterology Department of the V. Iverieli Endocrinology Metabolism Dietology Center, in Tbilisi, which offers outpatient services nationwide. All patients aged 18 and older with IBS, admitted to the outpatient clinic between 2020 and 2023, were eligible for participation. The diagnosis of IBS was made using the Rome IV criteria. A total of 287 patients were screened, and 89 were selected for inclusion in the study.

Patients with organic gastrointestinal diseases, clinical cases presenting “red flag” criteria, those diagnosed with *Helicobacter pylori* through a stool antigen test, and individuals with significant chronic conditions (such as cardiovascular, respiratory, liver, kidney diseases, or uncontrolled diabetes) or a history of cancer were excluded from the study. In the study group (n=89), 54.1% of participants were female, while 53% were male. The age distribution in the study group was as follows: 38 patients (42.7%) were aged 25-44 years, 33 patients (37.1%) were aged 45-64 years, and 18 patients (20.2%) were aged 65 and older.

Result

Depression was identified in 64 patients (71.91%) using the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale. Of these, 37.5% were diagnosed with moderate depression, while 62.5% were diagnosed with severe depression.

Early insomnia, characterized by difficulty falling asleep, affected 62 patients (69.7%). Middle insomnia, marked by frequent awakenings, anxiety, and restlessness during the night, was observed in 53 patients (59.6%). Additionally, 50 patients (56.2%) reported late insomnia, with complaints of waking up early in the morning and having difficulty falling back asleep. 58 patients (65.2%) of respondents experienced difficulties in performing their work and a loss of interest in activities they previously enjoyed. Among them, 3.3% were unable to work at all due to depression.

Somatic anxiety, characterized by complaints involving the gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, respiratory, and genitourinary systems, along with symptoms such as palpitations, headaches, and indigestion, was identified in 79 patients (88.8%). Gastrointestinal somatic symptoms, including loss of appetite, abdominal heaviness, and constipation, were present in 71 patients (79.8%). General somatic symptoms, such as heaviness in the limbs, back, or head; diffuse back pain; loss of energy, and fatigue, were observed in 88 patients, accounting for 98.9%.

Genital symptoms, including decreased libido and menstrual irregularities in women, were reported by 66 patients, accounting for 74.2% of respondents. Weight loss was observed in 40 patients (44.9%).

Discussion

Clinicians worldwide typically focus on psychological symptoms when diagnosing depression. However, this study reveals that somatic symptoms were identified in a significant proportion of patients. From the clinical practices, it is evident that patients often attribute these symptoms to other causes. Consequently, many physicians in Georgia, like other countries, become preoccupied with investigations for potential organic diseases, overlooking the possibility of depression as the underlying condition.

This research highlights the critical role of identifying somatic symptoms when formulating a treatment

plan for IBS patients and recommends HDRS-21 as an effective tool for diagnosing depression in masked form. By using this evaluation instrument, physicians can carefully assess symptoms that may be overlooked during the initial interview. It is essential to reduce the risk of disease recurrence.

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